

METHODS OF IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF DIAGNOSING THE MOTHER LANGUAGE ABILITY OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Annotation: In this article, information on improving the knowledge of primary school students in their native language and forming independent creative thinking skills, the problems of developing talent, the problems of developing interest in various forms of activity, and information is given.

Key words: school, education, person, success, professional activity, social meaning, talent, ability, enthusiasm, inclination, diligence, diligence, demandingness.

Improving the mechanisms for diagnosing the ability of primary school students in their native language requires the teacher to have high competence characteristics and modern educational technologies, information and computer technologies, methods of teaching the subject, It is intended to demonstrate general cultural and practical training of teachers.

The activity of primary school students is diagnosed based on the following indicators:

- the level of fulfillment of the requirements of state educational standards and educational programs;
- the general results of the final state certification of the students of the educational institution;
- general results of students in staged controls; students who have graduated from an educational institution continue their studies in academic lyceum, secondary special, vocational education institutions;
- district, regional and republican results of the "Knowledge Competition of Students of General Education Institutions on General Education Subjects";

- the results of the district and regional stages of the Science Olympiad;
- Results of "Language experts" and other examinations.
 - The second parameter of the principle of educational efficiency as indicators of "Organization of an effective diagnostic service in a general secondary educational institution":
 - the use of scientific-methodical, diagnostic and theoretical methods in studying the activities of teachers and students;
 - optimal organization of activities of a teacher, school psychologist and deputy head from a scientific and methodical point of view;
 - the existence and effectiveness of the mechanism that monitors the activity of students, teachers, school management by the public, studies parents, public opinion;
 - availability of analyzes representing the state, problems and shortcomings of educational institution management;
 - coordination of professional, scientific-methodical training of leading personnel with educational content and its methodological support;
 - increased level of theoretical, pedagogical, scientific-methodical training, ideological-political and spiritual-ethical, creative and social activity of school leaders;
 - the theoretical-methodological basis of the system of training the heads of the general secondary education school, in this process the attention is focused on the acquisition of methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the use of modern pedagogical, information and innovative technologies;
 - the head of the educational institution has the knowledge, skills and qualifications in the field of socio-psychological, communicative competence, culture and skills, as well as the ability to make the right decision and control its implementation, organizational skills;
 - the head of the educational institution has the skills to define an educational strategy to ensure the quality of the educational process;

- establishment of social cooperation between consumers of education and pedagogical service providers;
- the ability of the head of the educational institution to allocate time effectively, identify the problem competently, correctly define goals and tasks, and organize work among employees;
- the flexibility of the head of the educational institution: the ability to describe the dynamics of interpersonal relations in the team;
- the leadership of the head of the educational institution: the ability to solve problematic situations, the ability to stand out from others in terms of quality, initiative;
- the accessibility of the head of the educational institution: the ability to establish positive social relations, the ability to withstand mental stress and pressure are defined.

The next indicator is "The diagnosis of the quality of general secondary education is carried out on the basis of democratic principles." This indicator is evaluated based on the following indicators:

- the ability of the school director to manage the activities of teachers and students;
- supporting and encouraging student initiatives in the educational institution;
- taking into account the experience and level of training of teachers in the distribution of lessons in the section of classes;
- that students and teachers strictly adhere to the school's internal procedures;
- existence of a self-management system in the school;
- encouraging the activities of students with leadership skills;
- the formation of a friendly attitude towards healthy competition and self-critical assessment at school;
- the existence of a system for eliminating interpersonal conflicts in the educational institution;
- the creation of a working environment based on sincerity and mutual cooperation among students and teachers at the school;

- existence of a support system for students' initiatives;
- the extent to which the conditions in the educational institution satisfy students and parents have been studied and analyzed;
- the creation of an internal system of monitoring and ensuring the quality of education in accordance with the suggestions and requests of students, parents and other interested parties;
- participation of representatives of teachers and parents in the development and implementation of current and future plans of the educational institution;
- inclusion of parents' representatives in the school's internal management system;
- communication with graduates, students and parents using the information provided;
- it consists of the creation of a system of organizing extracurricular and extracurricular activities at the level of requirements in order to develop the intellectual abilities of students and to form independent thinking skills.

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